

ABSTRACT

Objectives: To examine whether the characteristics of patients hospitalized for hip fracture differed according to whether they lived in institutional or community residences.

Design: Prospective cohort study.

Setting: Six hospitals in the Barcelona area, Spain.

Participants: 872 consecutive patients (75.8% women, mean age 82.5 years) admitted for fall-related hip fracture.

Measurements: Sociodemographic data, geriatric assessment, and characteristics (location, time and possible cause: intrinsic, extrinsic, or combined risk factor) of falls leading to hip fracture.

Results: A total of 724 (83%) patients were living in the community and 148 were institutionalized. Multivariate analysis showed a predominance of female sex, married status, and better Barthel Index values and Charlson comorbidity scores among community-dwelling patients. In contrast, institutionalized patients were more often male and widowed, had more dementia and visual deficits, and presented higher levels of both total and psychoactive drug consumption. Although both groups fell more often in their place of residence, the proportion of community-dwelling patients falling in an exterior location was significantly higher. A history of previous falls was more common among institutionalized subjects.

Conclusion: In elderly patients suffering a hip fracture due to a fall there are some differences according to the place of residence. A high percentage of patients had suffered repeated falls.